

THE ORIGIN OF MUSIC AND ITS ROLE IN CULTURAL TOURISM OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The article discusses various theories of the origin of music and its role in the promotion of cultural tourism in Uzbekistan. Moreover, the article describes ancient musical instruments and the origins of music in the connection to nature and religion are considered. Special attention is paid to Uzbek national songs such as makom and shashmakom, the history of development of musical culture of Uzbekistan and its place in the modern world is also presented.*

Keywords: *music, musical instrument, nature, religion, makom, shashmakom, festival.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu ilmiy maqolada musiqa qadimgi kelib chiqish tarixi va uning O'zbekistonda madaniy turizmni rivojlantirishdagi o'rni haqidagi turli nazariyalar muhokama keltirildi. Bundan tashqari, maqolada qadimgi cholg'u asboblari tahlili keltirilgan, musiqa kelib chiqishi tabiat va din bilan bog'liqligi ko'rib chiqiladi. Shuningdek, maqom va shashmaqom kabi o'zbek milliy kuy-qo'shiqlariga alohida e'tibor qaratilib, O'zbekiston musiqa madaniyatining rivojlanish tarixi, uning zamonaviy dunyoda tutgan o'rni haqida ham ma'lumot berildi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *musiqa, cholg'u, tabiat, din, maqom, shashmakom, festival.*

Özet. *Makalede müziğin kökenine ilişkin çeşitli teoriler ve müziğin Özbekistan'da kültür turizminin desteklenmesindeki rolü tartışılmaktadır. Ayrıca makalede eski müzik aletleri anlatılmakta ve müziğin doğa ve dinle bağlantılı kökenleri ele alınmaktadır. Makom ve Şaşmakom gibi Özbek milli şarkılarına özel önem verilmekte, Özbekistan müzik kültürünün gelişim tarihi ve modern dünyadaki yeri de sunulmaktadır.*

Anahtar kelimeler: *müzik, çalgı, doğa, din, makom, şaşmakom, festival.*

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются различные теории происхождения музыки и её роль в развитии культурного туризма в Узбекистане. Кроме того, в статье описываются старинные музыкальные инструменты и рассматриваются связь музыки с природой и религией. Особое внимание уделено узбекским национальным песням, таким как маком и шашмаком, также представлена история развития музыкальной культуры Узбекистана и её место в современном мире.*

Ключевые слова: *музыка, музыкальный инструмент, природа, религия, маком, шашмаком, фестиваль.*

Music is an art form that uses sound organized in time (Wikipedia, 2024). It is created by combining different elements such as melody, harmony, rhythm, and timbre to evoke emotions and communicate ideas. Today Musical field is one the ways to the bright future in Uzbekistan which is also preserve history and it is presented as crucial part of cultural part of the country's life. The purpose of this research is to study the origin of music and its impact on cultural life of Uzbekistan. The Origin of Music is one of those topics that little discussed in Uzbekistan, there is a possibility it may lay the foundation of new ways in the musical industry. However, despite this, the civilians of Republic of Uzbekistan are reached impressive results in the field of music by presenting and using traditional musical instruments which origination goes back to very distant times. It's thought that Origin of Music goes to unknown times where the human civilization was only in an initial stage of evolution, so this research will touch the important, basic and related

historical and archeological topics beyond the history of Uzbekistan so that research can share more compelling explanations.

Theories about appearance of Music

Richard James Burgess in his book "The history of production of Music" (2014) makes a clear and exact statement which claims that we do not know when people firstly made music. However, there are several theories linked with the nature that makes a sense. The Greek Philosopher Aristotle (384-322 BCE) said that sound is the movement of air (Burgess, R. J. 2014), based on that person with high probability can imagine that the wind instruments were first hand-made source of receiving enjoyment from sound. This idea might be supported with the historical artifact "Neanderthal Flute" which was discovered in 1995 in the "Cave of Divje Babe", based on the dating of the layer in which the flute was discovered, it is about 60,000-50,000 years old and belongs to the Old Stone Age (Narodni Muzej Slovenije, 2014). However, there is slight contradiction, the historical artifact was made by people from the Paleolithic Age who claims to be Neanderthals, whose brain was not at that level in which it is possible to create such instrument and get pleasure from playing, so it is brainwashing from mass media and people cannot rely and base on such information and in result it returns to the statement of Burgess. After all, the discussion on the origin of music begins with the recognition that music is the combination of sounds that provide pleasure and enjoyment to humans. Researchers have indicated that humans possess a unique ability to capture, comprehend, and arrange these sounds to their liking. Moreover, the human capacity for sound reproduction and rhythm is unparalleled, whereas animals are confined to specific sounds across various senses, such as the enigmatic sound production of whales through pulsing water or expressing certain sounds. Additionally, it highlights the exclusion of well-known bird songs and suggests that while these sounds may bring pleasure to humans, the act of producing them is unconscious for the birds, as it depends on their evolved singing techniques and the supply of air (Stanford & Forsyth, 1930). This in turn results in a diversity of creatures in the environment that are capable of producing sounds through different senses, and there are limitations in some activities in which humans are superior to everyone else in this field. When it comes to the superiority of man in the field of music, it is imprinted in the history of the development of human civilization in ancient times, when each emerging nation began to develop its own traditions, cultures, religious beliefs and where music to some extent played a significant role.

Musical influences reached almost all civilizations throughout the history of human-kind. Musical heritage of countries like Egypt, Greece and Rome goes back thousands of years. One of the beliefs of Egyptians was that music is a gift from the gods and had a powerful impact on the human soul, the ancient Egyptians used various musical instruments such as the harp, lute, flute and various types of percussion instruments. Music was of great importance in their culture and was used in religious rites, ceremonies, celebrations and for entertainment (Martens, 1925). Ancient Greeks had a strong musical tradition, and their beliefs about music were closely intertwined with their mythology. In Greek and Rome mythologies, music was linked to the god Apollon, who was revered as the patron of music and the arts. The lyre was considered a symbolic instrument of music and poetry and was often associated with Apollon. The music of Ancient Rome was an integral part of religious and cultural rituals. It often accompanied dramatic performances, processions, and military events, and was also used in private and public celebrations. The music was primarily vocal, with instruments such as lyres, flutes, and trumpets

also playing a significant role. (Murray, 2017). Till our days the musical field of those times are still kept in the traditions and cultural heritage of these countries.

The first musical influences in the History of Uzbekistan

Music is an integral part of cultural life of Uzbekistan which have hundred years of rich tradition. The music of Uzbekistan has significantly evolved over the years, blending traditional and modern influences. Traditional Uzbek music has its roots in classical and folk forms, featuring instruments such as the Doira, Rubab, and tanbur. Uzbekistan's style of music is presented in several types and some of the most famous ones are Makom and Shashmakom. These style of music are indeed a significant genre in Uzbek music, with deep roots that continue to remain relevant in contemporary Uzbek culture. They are playing an important role in preserving and promoting traditions in Uzbekistan, as well as in the development of the modern music industry. Maqam has its origins in the 4th century AD, but the specific Central Asian tradition known as Makom started to develop in the 11th-12th centuries. However, shashmakom, a classical music style from Central Asia, is thought to have originated in Bukhara and Samarkand in the late 16th century (Wikipedia, 2023). Throughout of these long periods Uzbekistan succeeded to form of its own multiple Musical styles, but presently we have no idea nor database neither about how music was introduced in territory of Uzbekistan. Although we do not have accurate and reliable data about this, we do have information about how Western musical instruments were introduced into the territories of Uzbekistan. According to some sources, when the Russian Empire began to exert cultural influence on the region, Western musical instruments were first used in the early and mid-19th century. After this event, these instruments began to be widely used in the musical culture of this country. Many Uzbek musicians began to incorporate Western instruments such as piano, violin, guitar, etc. into their performances and compositions. This has led to the emergence of new genres and styles of music that combine traditional Uzbek elements with Western sounds. Thus, the use of Western musical instruments had a significant impact on the development of Uzbek musical culture.

Presentation of Music from Uzbekistan in 2023

In 2023, the Uzbekistan's progression is mirrored in the art of music where individuals witness the rise of new talented musicians utilizing their voices and instruments to communicate themes of love, liberation and social solidarity. In its turn music also serves as a unifying force, bringing people from different cultures together to help create a more harmonious society. This demonstrates the interconnectedness of global advancement and musical evolution as music becomes a potent catalyst for motivation, enlightenment and the reinforcement of universal principles. Uzbekistan is becoming a popular destination for music festivals, carnivals, concerts and etc. Attractions on the towns of Uzbekistan such as "Registan" and "Samarkand city" in Samarkand, "Magic City" in Tashkent create a stunning and wonderful atmosphere for musical performances. In the middle of this year, concerts were held by famous singers and musicians, representatives of different countries and nationalities, which in due time contributed to the development of the country's music industry, for instance 25th of November there were conducted the concerts of famous rappers or festive performances by singers. According to these impressive achievements Uzbekistan may expect the success in this field in the coming future. The future of the music industry is a captivating and constantly changing subject, featuring a multitude of potential advancements and innovations on the horizon. Music will most likely be followed the same trends we are seeing in modern technology. It will be incredibly social similar to social media, it will become increasingly computer-based and A.I. driven, and lastly, it will serve as a

window to the past, held open by any musicians continuing to create music in more traditional way (Sage Audio, 2023). Since most of the ways of presentations of music by Uzbekistan in traditional way, the rich heritage will not be lost because the powerful national melodies and expressive harmonies of the music of Uzbekistan resonate within the soul and leave a lasting imprint on the listener's heart.

Conclusion

In this research the evolution and development of music was explained by providing from the statements of researchers about the natural production of sounds to the ancient times where full of various convictions and mythologies somehow form the concept of appearance of music. Comparing the concept from the times of origins up to the present day, there is a big, even massive difference, but as a result, music remains a sphere of activity that changes with the development of human civilizations, that is, with each cognitive achievement of man, music appears in an improved form, evidence for this is given in this research, from mythological beliefs to Artificial Intelligence capable of producing and combining sounds without the presence of musical instruments. Its important that traditional form of this art should remain unchanged, since the music provides not only pleasant melodies, but because the presentation must correspond to the composition, and one of the countries that leads in that area of preservation of traditions is Uzbekistan.

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